

Assessment of Planning as a Management Tool in Construction Project Delivery, Kaduna state (Nigeria).

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Abstract

Planning is an essential management tool in construction project delivery. The Nigerian construction industry has been faced with various challenges ranging from; delays in construction project delivery and other associated problems, these have resulted in disputes, arbitration, total abandonment of projects, and protracted litigation by the parties. These problems have been associated with planning and scheduling; these challenges are known as the internal factors in an organization that cause a delay in construction project delivery. This study seeks to examine contractors' perceptions of what planning entails, the causes of construction planning failure, and problems that effective cost planning can avoid. Questionnaires were used to source information from respondents, particularly Builders, Architects, Quantity Surveyors, and Engineers. These 120 questionnaires were administered to professionals in the companies that were involved in the execution of construction work; popularly referred to as site engineers. The questionnaires solicited information relating to respondents' perception of the effectiveness of construction planning in the organization, possible ways of improving planning, causes of construction planning failure, and how to improve planning. Furthermore, a Relative Important Index (RII) was used to analyze the data. It was established that completeness of project documents was the most important part of planning having an RII result of 0.95. Nevertheless, the least impactful criteria were setting of cost, quality, and time having 0.85. The study

established that appropriate planning in a construction project will enable successful project delivery and adequate return on investment.

Keywords: construction management planning, construction project, project delivery

1. INTRODUCTION

Planning and controlling construction projects involves defining the activities, actions, time, cost, duration, and performance which will result in the successful completion of the project. Previous studies attributed insufficient construction planning to construction companies; this insufficiency in construction planning contributed to their low productivity, profitability, time overrun and cost overrun. Construction planning is a fundamental and challenging activity in the management and execution of construction projects (Khalid, 2017). Emad (2009) opined that construction project planning is similar to every project planning, this is because construction projects are characterized by a similar project life cycle like any other project.

According to Aibinu and Jagboro (2002), a major criticism facing the Nigerian construction industry is the growing rate of delays in construction project delivery and other associated problems. often result in disputes, arbitration, total abandonment, and protracted litigation by the parties. These problems, according to Odeyinka and Yusif (1997) are associated with planning and scheduling, they are internal factors in an organization that causes a delay in construction project delivery.

Every project involves the accomplishment of distinct or interconnected stages, these stages are conceptualization, planning, execution, and completion, and they are termed the project life cycle. For a project to be successful, every aspect of its needs should be prepared or planned. Project planning was defined by PM BOK (2000) as that stage of a project that identifies the project activities and how each will be accomplished. Planning a project aims to identify each major task, estimate the time and resources required, and provide a framework for management or owners to review and control its progress. This study aims to assess construction project planning and controlling of contractors to enhance their performance.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Questionnaires were used to source information from respondents, the respondents included Builders, Architects, Quantity Surveyors, and Engineers. Out of the 120 questionnaires, 20 questionnaires were each purposive distributed among the professionals. The Questionnaire was designed to solicit information relating to respondents' perception of what construction planning entails, how their organizations plan construction projects, and which professional is responsible for the planning. Bamisile (2014) attributed the responsibility of planning construction projects to project managers; hence the questionnaire was administered to project managers in each organization.

Also, questionnaires were administered to professionals in each company that is involved in the execution of the work; popularly referred to as site engineers. The questionnaires solicited information relating to respondents' perception of the effectiveness of construction planning in the organization, possible ways of improving planning, causes of construction planning failure, and how to improve planning.

2.1 Relative Importance Index (RII)

Relative Important Index was used to analyze the results of the questionnaires, this method has been to supplement multiple regression analysis; Relative Importance Indices provide information that is not readily available from indices typically produced from multiple regressions (Scott and James, 2011). The Relative Importance Index (RII) will be determined by dividing the mean response by the highest value on the Likert scale to be used. A decision relating to the most significant factor will be taken based on the factor having the highest RII point in the group of the identified variables.

Subsequently, statistical mean scores and standard deviation were used to analyze the data acquired, and Likert's five-point scale was used to analyze the responses of the respondents.

Table 1: Five Likert Rating Scale

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Grade Point	5	4	3	2	1
Range	4.5 – 5.0	3.5 – 4.4	2.5 – 3.4	1.5– 2.5	0.5 – 1.4

The formula for the mean $(\bar{x}) = \frac{\sum fx}{\sum f}$

(1)

Where: fx = Total frequency and f = Frequency

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Contractor's Perception of What Construction Planning Entails

Based on Figure 1, the process and activities of construction planning have been identified as Ensuring completeness of documents, the precise definition of a construction project, establishing the client's needs, and appropriate project team, identifying available project resources and constraints, defining exact project duration, identify a mechanism for scope review, and lastly, setting of cost, quality and time (Chitkara (2012)). For activities that form part of planning construction as identified in Figure 1, respondents were asked to rank how they agree each of the activities be part of the construction plan. The ranking as shown in Table 1, was strongly disagree, disagree, undecided, agree, or strongly agree.

Figure 1: Contractor's perception of what planning entails

The result established that ensuring completeness of project documents including specifications and all drawings was the most important part of planning having an RII result of 9.5. However, the least impactful was the setting of cost, quality, and time having 0.85 which is also significant. Besides, the aforementioned points in Figure 1 are in agreement with the definition of what planning should include, the result further showed agreement between literature and practice, because contractors show agreement with construction planning activities as outlined by previous studies (Chitkara (2012)). For a construction project plan to have an excellent chance of succeeding there is a need for planners to ensure all activities identified in Figure 1 are achieved satisfactorily at planning on how to execute any project.

Figure 2 : Problems that effective cost planning can avoid

Figure 2 shows agreement between contractors and the previous recommendation of Oladimeji and Ojo (2012), this is indicated by respondents agreeing that planning construction projects can avoid cost overrun foremost with a Relative importance index (RII) of 0.88, then the ability to avoid time overrun (RII=0.86) and is likely to avoid compromise in construction project quality (RII=0.86). The ability of construction project planning to avoid the dissatisfaction of customers was ranked 10th with an RII of 0.71, the ability of construction project planning to avoid abandonment of the project was ranked 9th with an RII index of 0.72 while the ability of construction project planning to avoid bad name to the organization was ranked 8th with RII of 0.75.

3.2 Causes of Construction Planning Failure

Chitkara (2009) The financial integrity of the client and inadequate resources budgeted for planning, The ethical standard of the client and wrong estimates are identified factors that can lead a construction project planning to fail, a list of the identified causes was presented to respondents who were asked to indicate how much they agree or disagree with each of the factors that can cause a project plan to

fail on a five-point Likert scale. The relative importance index (RII) was used to rank each factor as agreed or disagreed by the respondents.

Figure 3: Causes of Construction Planning Failure

From Figure 3, it can be seen that respondents agree that all the identified factors can cause construction project planning to fail. This is indicated by the RII of the least agreed factor which is significant having an RII result of 0.77. The financial integrity of the client and inadequate resources budgeted for planning both had an RII of 0.94 and are ranked first. The ethical standard of the client and wrong estimates both had an RII of 0.92 and are ranked as the second most important factor that can cause construction project planning failure. However, disregarding project management rules had the least RII result of 0.77. The result agreed with the study conducted by Dahiru & Mohammed (2012), study attributed the failure of a

construction project to finance, communication, and client-related factors, this result further buttresses client-related factors that lead to failure of construction planning to be client-ethical standard and client financial integrity.

4. CONCLUSION

The study examined contractors' perceptions of what planning entails, causes of construction planning failure, and problems that effective cost planning can avoid. The analysis was carried out using the Relative Important Index (RII). The analysis identified that ensuring the completeness of project documents including specifications and all drawings was the most important part of planning having an RII result of 9.5. However, the least impactful was the setting of cost, quality, and time having 0.85 which was also significant. For the causes of construction failure, it was decided that the financial integrity of the client and inadequate resources budgeted for planning had RII of 0.94 each and are ranked first. The ethical standard of the client and wrong estimates both had an RII of 0.92 and are ranked second. While the disregard for project management rules had the least RII result of 0.77. Lastly, the respondents agreed that planning construction projects could avoid cost overrun with an RII of 0.88, then the ability to avoid time overrun (RII=0.86) and avoid compromise in construction project quality (RII=0.86). The study suggests that good planning in a construction project can go a long way in delivering a successful project.

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